

PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATION OF STATIVE VERBS IN ENGLISH AND
UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation – This article gives information about mental verbs and their role in the literature. In the Uzbek language, different variants of mental stative verbs such as “hadiksiramoq”, “qadrlamoq”, “magrurlanmoq”, “qanoatsizlanmoq” and “toqatsizlanmoq” are considered. Verbs such as “struggle”, “contemplate”, “conceive”, and “despise” in English have also been analyzed by considering that their semantics can be expressed in Uzbek through different verbs.

Keywords and phrases – mental verbs, stative verbs, literary translation, linguistic phenomena, lexical unit, lexical-semantic unit, Oriental literature, polysemy, informal alternative, plot-oriented.

Annotatsiya – Ushbu maqolada ruhiy holat fe’llari va uning adabiyotda tutgan o’rni va roli haqida ma’lumotlar berib o’tilgan. O‘zbek tilida “hadiksiramoq”, “qadrlamoq”, “magrurlanmoq”, “qanoatsizlanmoq” va “toqatsizlanmoq” kabi ruhiy holat fe’llarining bir-biriga nomutanosiblik variantlari ko‘rib chiqilgan. Shuningdek, ingliz tilidagi “struggle”, “contemplate”, “conceive”, “despise” kabi fe’llar ham semalari o‘zbek tilida turli fe’llar vositasida anglatilishi mumkinligi ko‘rib chiqib tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so‘zlar va iboralar – ruhiy holat fe’llari, holat fe’llari, badiiy tarjima, til hodisalari, leksik-semantik birlik, Sharq adabiyoti, polisemiya, norasmiy muqobil, syujetli.

Аннотация – В этой статье дается информация о ментальных глаголах и их роли в литературе. В узбекском языке рассматриваются различные варианты ментальных глаголов состояния, такие как «hadiksiramoq», «qadrlamoq», «magrurlanmoq», «qanoatsizlanmoq» и «toqatsizlanmoq». Такие глаголы, как «struggle», «contemplate», «conceive» и «despise» в английском языке, также были проанализированы с учетом того, что их семантика может быть выражена в узбекском языке с помощью различных глаголов.

Ключевые слова и словосочетания – ментальные глаголы, глаголов состояния, художественный перевод, языковые явления, лексическая единица, лексико-семантическая единица, восточная литература, полисемия, неформальная альтернатива, сюжетно-ориентированный.

The translation is a type of science and art that formed as a result of this person's efforts to open up to the world and discover the world for himself. Unlike journalistic, oral, or scientific translation, the translation of a literary text requires a high level of skill and creativity from a specialist. Indeed, "the translator of a literary text does not depict the original in another language like photography but recreates it. A translator is not only required to know a foreign language, his creative ability, and potential must also be sufficient to recreate the author's work in translation".¹ However, no matter how free the process is, literary translation also puts a certain task in front of the specialist and therefore limits it. In particular, the text of the translation must be suitable to the original text, there should be mentioned the style and thoughts of the writer.

One of the most important tasks of specialists is to translate works in English directly into Uzbek, as well as to translate masterpieces of Uzbek literature into English. Literary and linguists are responsible for the theoretical justification of problems in the translation process and recommendations for overcoming these problems. Improving the works of translation, and raising their artistic and methodological level requires a comparative study of linguistic phenomena as a field. Because the study of linguistic phenomena as a field allows us to generalize the means at each level, it also helps to determine the characteristics of a particular element at different levels. Understanding the parallels and asymmetries in the linguistic and semantic parameters of the same field tools in different languages should serve to perfect the translation of these tools.

It is natural for lexical-semantic fields to be parallel in different constructed languages, but mental state verbs are an exception. Like other types of verbs, this group has the same classification in both Uzbek and English, which means that alternatives can be used in the mutual translation of these means. At a glance, this hypothesis eliminates the possibility of all the problems that can occur in translation. Therefore, the work of art should have an educational value that includes the realities of life and didactic philosophy². Of course, like any product of creative thinking, a work of art has an individual character. However, aside from the methodological and narrative peculiarities, the predominance of plot over the image in English literature, in which the writer "catches" the reader's attention mainly through the sequence of events should be admitted that it is a general aspect peculiar to English literature.

Uzbek classical literature was formed based on Islamic philosophy. In the works, the inner truths are pointed out through the image of the external world. The traditions of classical literature which is formed over the centuries are also reflected in modern works of art. Modern Uzbek literature addresses a variety of social issues. Although it

¹Chukovskiy K. Gumilev N. Printsipy xudojstvennogo perevoda vseмирnaya literatura - SPB: 1919 - p. 61

²Alekseev M. From the history of English literature. Etyudy, ocherki, issledovaniya - M.: Goslitizdat, 1960. - p. 499

does not cover the subject of religious studies in classical literature, there is a didactic spirit in these works as well. Although the situation, the person, and the image of the view do not express more divine inner meaning, it serves to express the writer's mood, his attitude towards the event, the character, and the behavior of the characters³. Thus, in both modern and classical Uzbek literature, along with the plot, the expressiveness of the means is of great importance. In works, word choice is made not only according to the meaning of the noun but also according to its contextual function. It is known that the lexical-semantic paradigm of the Uzbek language is distinguished by the polysemy of nouns, their meaning, and expression. Therefore, the fact that the stative verbs, which have the same meaning in English and Uzbek, are parallel in semantic composition. For example, the following verbs in Uzbek have their alternatives in English, although the semantic structure of these means may be disproportionate to each other.

DICTIONARY UNIT	NAMING	EXPRESSION
HADIKSIRAMOQ	<i>hadik olmoq; xayfsiramoq, cho'chimoq, qo'rqmoq</i>	<i>ikkilanmoq, shubhalanmoq; uzluklilik, noaniqlik, salbiy bo'yoqdorlik, tafakkur holati</i>
QADRLAMOQ	<i>Obro'-e'tiboriga, qadr-qimmatiga yarasha izzat-hurmat ko'rsatmoq, qadr qilmoq; Ahamiyatiga, qimmatiga yarasha e'tibor bermog, shunga yarasha munosabatda bo'lmoq.</i>	<i>mehr bermog, afzal ko'rmoq davomiylilik, uzluklilik, ijobiy bo'yoqdorlik, hissiy holat</i>

In the above examples, the narrowing point of the asymmetry is on the English side, to be more concrete, stative verbs in Uzbek differ from their English equivalents of semantics. The fact that the meaning of each noun or phrase in these words is expressed in English by a separate verb, requires the selection of a different translation unit in a different context.

Such asymmetry can also be reversed. In other words, the meaning of different terms in different contexts of mental stative verbs in English may have a broader semantic expression than their Uzbek equivalents. In this case, a stative verb in English has several alternatives in Uzbek. Choosing a suitable translation unit according to the general content of the text requires perfect knowledge of the lexical level of both

³Mirvaliev S. Uzbek writers - Tashkent: Science, 1993 - p.157

languages and skill from the translator, for example, in English, these verbs are required to have several meanings of expressions, while in Uzbek each of these semantics is required to be translated by a separate lexical unit. The semantics of a stative verb in English can be expressed in Uzbek using different verbs.

DICTIONARY UNIT	NAMING	EXPRESSION
STRUGGLE	<i>to experience difficulty and make a very great effort to do something; to move somewhere with great effort; to be in danger of failing or being defeated</i>	<i>continuous and uncompleted manner, positive stylistic meaning, emotional state</i>
CONTEMPLATE	<i>to spend time considering a possible future action, or to consider one particular thing for a long time in a serious and quiet way</i>	<i>meaning of expectation, planning, continuous and uncompleted manner, neutral stylistic meaning, mental state</i>

It is understood that the imbalance of semantic content between stative verbs in the two languages is one of the features that complicate the translation of these elements in the literary text. Semantic asymmetry, the state of mind in a language, the number of polysemy, or the number of semantics is found in both English and Uzbek languages. In this case, asymmetry is caused by polysemy in the sense of naming and expression.

There may also be periodic imbalances between translation units in some cases. In most cases, the translator translates a mental state verb that is used repeatedly in the text into another word that expresses the same meaning to avoid tautology in the translated text. Thus sometimes there is a periodic imbalance between the unit of translation and the unit of originality

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